

Token-based typology and word order entropy:

A study based on Universal Dependencies

Abstract

The present paper discusses the benefits and challenges of token-based typology, which takes into account the frequencies of words and constructions in language use. This approach makes it possible to introduce new criteria for language classification, which would be difficult or impossible to achieve with the traditional, type-based approach. This point is illustrated by a case study of word order variation, which can be measured as entropy at different levels of granularity. I argue that this variation can be explained by general functional mechanisms and pressures, which manifest themselves in language use, such as conventionalization of frequent patterns, optimization of processing and avoidance of ambiguity. The case studies are based on data from the Universal Dependencies corpora and Leipzig Corpora Collection.

Keywords: corpora, word order, frequency, Universal Dependencies, entropy

1. Token-based typology and word order variation

The present paper reflects on the role of usage frequencies with regard to the fundamental goals of typology: language classification and identification and explanation of cross-linguistic generalizations (cf. Croft 2003: 1–2). In most typological research, languages have been treated as single data points with a categorical value (e.g. OV or VO, prepositional or postpositional). The overwhelming majority of typological universals (e.g. the ones found in

The Universals Archive at the University of Konstanz¹) are of this kind. Similarly, the influential World Atlas of Language Structures (Dryer & Haspelmath 2013) contains only categorical or ordinal variables, which characterize language types. I'll refer to this approach as **type-based**.

In contrast, **token-based typology** makes generalizations and classifies languages by using the tokens of specific linguistic units or structures observed in language use, as approximated by corpora. It can also use aggregate variables derived from the distributions of usage tokens, such as entropy, complexity, average dependency length, etc. Unlike in the type-based approach, the variables are continuous and reflect language-internal variation. This is a growing area of research, which has been boosted by an increasing number of multilingual corpora, which are becoming available nowadays. These corpora range from translations of popular children's books like *Harry Potter*, to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and from Wikipedia articles to collections of spoken traditional narratives (see information about several multilingual corpora in the Supplementary Materials). Corpora have been recently used for diverse goals in recent typological and comparative research, such as the following:

- testing of general functional laws and principles, e.g. the correspondence between frequency and coding asymmetries (Haspelmath et al. 2014), Zipf's law of abbreviation (Zipf 1935; Benz & Ferrer-i-Cancho 2015) and effects of average surprisal on word length (Piantadosi et al. 2011);
- explanation of common cross-linguistic patterns, e.g. discussion of ergativity in terms of preferred argument structure (e.g. Du Bois et al. 2003, Haig & Schnell 2016b);
- induction of cross-linguistically salient dimensions of conceptual variation with the help of probabilistic semantic maps (e.g. Wälchli & Cysouw 2012; Levshina 2015);
- language classification based on quantitative indices derived from corpora, e.g. different measures of linguistic complexity on the basis of the Kolmogorov complexity and entropy (e.g. Juola 1998; Koplenig et al. 2017).

By using continuous variables instead of categorical ones, one can capture intra-linguistic variation, which is ubiquitous in language, and avoid the existing bias towards a restricted set of word order patterns, which display low language-internal variability and

¹ <https://typo.uni-konstanz.de/archive/intro/index.php>, last access 18.12.2017.

cross-linguistic bimodal distributions (Wälchli 2009; see also Section 3.2). As put by Diessel, “language consists of fluid structures and probabilistic constraints that are shaped by communication, memory, and processing” (2017: 2). In this paper I want to demonstrate the typological relevance of intra-linguistic variation, which emerges as the result of such probabilistic constraints and different performance pressures.

For illustration, I will focus on word order. This domain has been thoroughly investigated on the basis of categorical typological data, especially the correlations between different word order patterns (e.g. Greenberg 1963; Vennemann 1974; Lehmann 1978; Dryer 1992; Dunn et al. 2011, to name just a few). There has been corpus-based work on word order, as well. In particular, Wälchli (2009) studied the verb–locative order in the New Testament translations, zooming in on specific contexts, such as the imperative domain. Östling (2015) investigated the word order in the New Testament in almost 1000 languages in order to produce more data for the languages missing in the WALS datasets. Liu (2010) used treebanks to investigate the continuum between head-initial and head-final languages. Guzmán Naranjo & Becker (2018) focused on correlations between verb-headed and noun-headed dependencies in the Universal Dependencies corpora.

In this study, I will focus on one aspect of word order typology that is impossible without the token-based approach, namely, on word order variability. This aspect has received less attention in general linguistics and typology than the word order correlations, although it was quite prominent in formal linguistics in the 1980s. It was argued, in particular, that languages belong to two main categories: configurational and non-configurational. Unlike configurational languages (the standard example being English, as usual), non-configurational languages exhibit relatively free word order along with other characteristics, such as extensive use of zero anaphoras (or pro-drop), the use of discontinuous expressions and rich case systems (Hale 1982, 1983). Examples are Warlpiri (Hale 1983), Japanese (Chomsky 1981) and Hungarian (Kiss 1987). At the same time, individual languages tend to exhibit these properties to different degrees, which makes one doubt that configurationality as a single typological parameter exists (Rögnvaldsson 1995). Moreover, as will be shown in this paper, there is no such thing as absolutely rigid or absolutely free word order, and whereas some patterns in one language are more fixed, others may be more flexible. For example, even configurational languages like English allow for some variation, e.g. the subject – verb inversion in *In the middle of the room stood an antique*

mahogany table. At the same time, the word order in non-configurational languages is not completely free, either. For example, as will be shown in Section 3.1, the subject – object order in Japanese, a presumably non-configurational language, does not exhibit substantially more variation than the same pattern in English, and has in fact more rigid order in several other patterns. From this follows that the notion of configurationality is not particularly useful for predicting the actual language use, which is the primary focus of the present paper.

On the functional side, there has also been some work on word order variability. One of the central questions has been to what extent pragmatic factors influence the order in different languages. In some languages like English the order of elements is determined mostly by their syntactic functions, while in the other languages the word order is influenced to a large extent by the pragmatic order of topic and comment, definite and indefinite referents, given and new information, newsworthiness, etc. (Givón 1984: Ch. 6; Payne 1992). Examples are Czech, Warlpiri and Ojibwa. Among such languages, one can also make more subtle distinctions. For instance, Czech speakers are highly sensitive to what constitutes ‘natural’ word order, while there is no such order in languages like Cayuga (Iroquoian, spoken in the USA) and Ngandi (Gunwinyguan, spoken in Australia) (Mithun 1992). Instead of using some marked word order for the purposes of focus, as one would do in Czech, the speakers will use additional morphological marking. These studies usually investigate a limited number of languages and only a selection of word order patterns, due to the high costs of manual analysis of such data, and are often mostly qualitative and corpus-illustrated, rather than quantitative and corpus-driven.

With the growing number of available corpora, one can work out objective criteria and procedures for quantification of word order variation. One can also compute and compare variability measures on different levels of abstraction for a large number of languages and word order patterns. Moreover, one can try to understand how this variability is related to other linguistic parameters and universal functional constraints, and test the hypotheses statistically. These are the goals of the present paper.

The data for the case studies are taken from the Universal Dependencies corpora 2.1 (Nivre et al. 2017) and some corpora from the Leipzig Corpora Collection (Goldhahn et al. 2012) analysed with the help of the Universal Dependencies pipeline (Straka & Straková 2017), implemented in the R package *udpipe* (Wijffels 2018). Using these data, I compute the proportions of possible orders, e.g. determiner + Noun and Noun + Determiner, and derive

different measures from these proportions, such as Shannon entropy or measures of dispersion. For confirmatory analyses, mixed-effects linear models are used. All statistical analyses presented below were performed with the help of R, free statistical software (R Core Team 2018). The datasets are provided in the Supplementary Materials.

The remaining part of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides information about the data from the Universal Dependencies corpora and the main quantitative concepts. In Section 3, I present the results of exploratory analyses of word order entropy both for individual languages, and for individual word order patterns, and provide explanations of this variation. Section 4 compares the word order variation at different levels of granularity, showing that some (but not all) variation at the level of abstract syntactic dependencies can be explained by the variation at the level of wordforms. In Section 5, I test some usage-based functional explanations that play a role in determining the variation of word order. In Section 6, I provide a summary of the findings and an outlook.

2. Data: The Universal Dependencies corpora

2.1. General introduction

The Universal Dependencies (UD) corpora, version 2.1, are a collection of 102 treebanks (i.e. syntactically parsed corpora) representing 60 languages from twelve different families, including one sign language (see the Supplementary Materials for a full list). They also contain varieties of one language: standard and non-standard Romanian, as well as European and Brazilian Portuguese. The cross-linguistic syntactic categories and parts of speech used in the UD corpora are the result of a long evolution. The definitions of cross-linguistic categories usually include both semantic and formal properties. For example, the direct (or rather non-indirect) object is defined as the most patient-like non-subject argument. One of the main goals and challenges of the UD project is to keep the annotation design satisfactory

both for language-specific analyses and for typological comparison.² This compromise is often achieved by assuming language-specific subclasses of the universal categories, e.g. *nummod:gov*, the numeric modifier governing the NP, which represents a subclass of numeric modifiers in Slavic (as in Russian *troje druzej* ‘three friends’, where the numeral is in the singular neuter form, and the counted noun takes the genitive case).

2.2. Dependencies and co-dependencies

The case studies presented in this paper are based on the frequencies of different word order patterns in the UD. More exactly, I use the frequencies of so-called heads and dependent elements, as well as some co-dependencies (e.g. subject and object of the same verbal predicate). The full list is given in Table 1. Note that the understanding of heads and dependents in the UD corpora is different from some syntactic theories. In particular, functional elements (adpositions, auxiliaries, subordinators) are coded as dependents, not as heads.³ One may agree or disagree with that approach, but it plays no role in the analyses that follow. The reason is that the central measure in this study, namely, entropy of the order of two elements X and Y, remains the same regardless of whether X is the head and Y is the dependent, or the other way round (see Section 2.3 for more details). The dependencies related to punctuation, coordination, various discourse markers, vocatives and multiword expressions were not taken into account. I also excluded the so-called root (the predicate of the main clause), which does not depend on anything, and dependencies which are infrequent in the UD sample of languages (e.g. classifiers). This selection presents the main dependencies in nominal phrases, verbal phrases, simple clauses and complex sentences. Nominal and pronominal subjects, objects, nominal modifiers and obliques were treated separately, since the order of nominal and pronominal constituents is often different. Subordinators in adverbial and complement clauses were extracted separately, as well, and so were adverbial modifiers of adjectives and verbs. Note that in the case of interclausal

² See more information at <http://universaldependencies.org/introduction.html>.

³ See more at <http://universaldependencies.org/u/overview/syntax.html>.

dependencies, the head is the predicate of the main clause or the head noun (for relative clauses), and the dependent element is the predicate of the subordinate clause.

Some contextual restrictions were made. Questions and exclamatory sentences were disregarded. Subjects, objects and obliques were only counted when they occurred in the main clause.

Type	Label in this study	Label in UD	Dependent	Head	Example
Nominals and their heads	nsubjNoun_Pred, nsubjPron_Pred	nsubj	Subject (noun or pronoun)	Predicate of the main clause (root)	Jane _{NSUBJ} reads _{HEAD} many books.
	objNoun_Pred, objPron_Pred	obj	Direct object (noun or pronoun)	Predicate of the main clause (root)	Jane reads _{HEAD} many books _{OBJ} .
	oblNoun_Pred, oblPron_Pred	obl	oblique phrase, i.e. NP encoded differently from the core arguments (noun or pronoun).	Predicate of the main clause (root)	Jane looks _{HEAD} at the stars _{OBL} .
	nmodNoun_Noun, nmodPron_Noun	nmod	Nominal dependent (noun or pronoun)	Noun	Jane is reading a book _{HEAD} on quantum mechanics _{NMOD} .
Co-dependent nominals	nsubj_obj	nsubj, obj	Nominal subject and nominal object	-	Jane _{NSUBJ} is reading a book _{OBJ} .
	obj_obl	obj, obl	Nominal object and nominal oblique phrase	-	Jane is reading a book _{OBJ} in the library _{OBL} .
Modifiers and their heads	nummod_Noun	nummod	Numeric modifier	Noun	Jane published ten _{NUMMOD} books _{HEAD} .
	amod_Noun	amod	Adjectival modifier	Noun	Jane is a famous _{AMOD} scholar _{HEAD} .
	advmod_Verb, advmod_Adj	advmod	Adverbial modifier	Verb or adjective	Jane writes _{HEAD} clearly _{ADVMOD} .

					genetically _{ADVMOD} modified _{HEAD} food
Function words and their heads	det_Noun	det	Determiner (article, possessive pronoun, demonstrative pronouns, etc.)	Noun	Jane is reading a _{DET} book _{HEAD} .
	adp_Noun	case	Adposition or clitic case marker	Noun	Jane _{HEAD} 's _{SCASE} recent book a recent book of _{CASE} Jane _{HEAD}
	aux_Verb	aux	Auxiliary (tense, mood, aspect, voice or evidentiality)	Verb	Jane is _{AUX} reading _{HEAD} .
	cop_Pred	cop	Copula	Any nominal	Jane is _{COP} honest _{HEAD} .
	mark_ccomp, mark_advcl	mark	Subordinators (complementizers or subordinating conjunctions)	Predicate of complement clause (mark_ccomp) or adverbial clause (mark_advcl)	Jane hopes that _{MARK} her paper appears _{HEAD} soon.
Clauses and their heads	csubj_Main	csubj	Clausal subject	Predicate of the main clause	What she said _{CSUBJ} makes _{HEAD} sense.
	ccomp_Main	ccomp	Clausal complement	Predicate of the main clause	Jane thinks _{HEAD} Peter cooks _{CCOMP} very well.
	acl_Noun	acl	Finite and non-finite clausal modifier (adjectival clause)	Noun	a book _{HEAD} that Jane wrote _{ACL}
	advcl_Main	advcl	Adverbial clause modifier	Predicate of the main clause	Jane was sad _{HEAD} when I talked _{ADVCL} to her.

Table 1. Word order patterns (syntactic dependencies and co-dependencies) considered in the present paper.

The counts of the selected word order patterns (e.g. Determiner + Noun) and their reverse orders (e.g. Noun + Determiner) were extracted from the Universal Dependencies

corpora with the help of a Python script. The dependencies with frequency less than 20 (usually due to the small size of some corpora) were excluded from the subsequent analyses. Overall, I had data from 101 corpora of 60 languages representing 24 genera and twelve families (counting Basque, Japanese, Korean and Swedish Sign Language as separate data points).

2.3. Shannon entropy

The main measure used in this study is Shannon entropy (Shannon 1948). It represents variation of word order in the twenty-four dependencies and co-dependencies described in the previous section. For each of the word order patterns in every UD corpus, I computed the entropy using the formula in (1):

$$(1) \quad H(X) = -\sum_{i=1}^2 P(x_i) \log_2 P(x_i)$$

where X is a binary variable representing two possible word orders, e.g. Determiner + Noun and Noun + Determiner. $P(x_i)$ is the probability of one of the orders, which equals its relative frequency (proportion) in the corpus. If the proportion of one word order, e.g. Determiner + Noun, is 1, and the proportion of the reverse order (e.g. Noun + Determiner) is 0, or the other way round, the entropy H is equal to zero. There is no variation. If the proportion of each of the possible word orders is 0.5, the entropy takes the maximum value of 1. If both orders are attested, and one of them is more frequent than the other, then the entropy lies between 0 and 1. For example, if the proportion of Determiner + Noun in a specific corpus is 0.9 (or 90%), and the proportion of Noun + Determiner is 0.1 (or 10%), then the entropy of this dependency is $H = -(0.9 \times \log_2(0.9) + 0.1 \times \log_2(0.1)) = 0.47$.

This measure can be computed at different levels of granularity. For example, one can use the level of abstract dependencies, as shown above. One can also compute entropy for

individual wordforms that represent dependencies, e.g. the entropy of *actively_ADV + VERB* and *Verb + actively_ADV*, where *actively* is an adverbial modifier of a verb. This approach will be discussed in Section 4.

It is important to note that word order entropy, as it is defined here, is a purely descriptive and data-driven measure based on actual word order patterns. It does not represent word order “freedom”. If a word or syntactic constituent can have different positions with regard to another element, this is not necessarily because it’s “free” in the sense “random” or dependent on the speaker’s whim. The reason is that it may be due to some usage constraints or due to insufficient granularity (see Section 4). The entropy is also different from flexibility. The former is a measure that shows only what is found in the data, while the latter represents the possibility that a given word order pattern can be changed in accordance to the speaker’s communicative needs. In comparison with freedom, flexibility and similar notions, entropy has an important methodological advantage: it is an objective measure, which can be straightforwardly applied for cross-linguistic comparisons.

2.4. Effect of different text types

Note also that the sizes of the UD corpora are very different, as well as their text types. One of the main challenges when working with cross-linguistic corpora is their representativeness and comparability of the text types (cf. Croft 2003: 112). There are no multilingual corpora at the moment that could be compared to the carefully sampled British National Corpus or similar standards. The existing multilingual corpora can represent one text (e.g. *Le Petit Prince* used by Stolz et al. 2017) or numerous texts of a few rather specific genres (e.g. OPUS by Tiedemann [2012] with film subtitles, European Parliament transcripts and technical documentation). Spoken data are only available in Multi-CAST. However, it only contains monologues. This is not surprising, since the annotation of spoken dialogical data is immensely time-consuming. Dialogical corpora are, however, of vital importance for discovering universals of conversational infrastructure (e.g. Dingemanse et al. 2013).

To what extent the text types are important for cross-linguistic comparisons is an empirical question. In order to check that for the word order patterns considered in this study, I performed a check based on the Leipzig Corpora Collection (Goldhahn et al. 2012),⁴ which consists of comparable corpora in diverse languages. I took the corpora that represent eight languages: Arabic, English, Finnish, Hindi, Indonesian, Russian, Turkish and Vietnamese. Three types of texts were selected: Wikipedia articles, online news and miscellaneous web content. Samples of 10,000 sentences of each text type in every language were annotated using the UDPipe software, which provides tokenization, lemmatization, part-of-speech annotation and Universal Dependencies parsing. Next, the word order frequencies were extracted using the general procedure described above, and the proportions of different word orders were computed, e.g. the proportion of adjectival modifiers followed by nouns in the total occurrences of adjectival modifiers before or after the head noun. The correlations between the word order proportions in the three text types within each language were very high, ranging from 0.85 to 0.995 (Pearson's product-moment correlation). I also computed the average entropy measures across the dependencies and co-dependencies for each subcorpus. The dot chart in Figure 1 shows the mean entropy scores. The results show that there is little difference. The greatest discrepancy is in Russian, where Wikipedia shows lower word order entropies on average than the two other text types, but the difference is still relatively modest.

⁴ <http://wortschatz.uni-leipzig.de/de/download> (last access 11.11.2018)..

Figure 1. Mean entropy scores for different text types in eight languages (data from the Leipzig Corpora Collection).

This observation is supported by the conclusion made by Liu (2010), who argues on the basis of empirical data that genre differences are not strong enough to influence the conclusions about dominant word order.

Some languages are also represented by texts from different historical periods. For example, Latin combines numerous sources, which include the Vulgate New Testament translations, Caesar, Cicero, Thomas Aquinas, etc. The high entropy in Latin, which will be demonstrated in Section 3.1, may be due to the fact that different authors who lived in different periods might have had different word order preferences. In order to explore that, I took several Classical and Medieval Latin texts from the online publications on Wikisource.⁵ The texts and their mean entropies are shown in Table 2. The numbers are high, which suggests that the high entropy in Latin is not an artefact of combining different texts from different time periods. In particular, all text exhibited variation in the position of copulas, adjectival modifiers, nominal modifiers and nominal objects with regard to their heads. Especially variable was the relative position of the co-dependents (SO/OS and OX/XO,

⁵ https://la.wikisource.org/wiki/Pagina_prima, last access 12.11.2018.

where X stands for the oblique nominal phrase), as one can see from the entropies that are very close to 1.

Table 2. Entropy in Classical and Medieval Latin texts. The number in brackets specifies the entropy without those dependencies that exhibited low frequencies in at least one of the texts and were discarded.

Author	Text	Period	Mean Entropy Head-Dep	Mean Entropy SO, OX
Caesar	Commentarii de Bello Gallico	58–49 BC	0.61 (0.66)	0.97
Cicero	De Fato	44 BC	0.77 (0.77)	0.95
Cicero	Cato Maior de Senectute	44 BC	0.76 (0.78)	0.97
Tacitus	De origine et situ Germanorum (Germania)	appr. 98 AD	0.73 (0.75)	0.95
Tacitus	Dialogus de oratoribus	appr. 102 AD	0.75 (0.77)	0.99
Seneca	De Clementia	55-56 AD	0.78 (0.80)	0.96
St. Augustine	Confessiones	397-400 AD	0.76 (0.86)	0.99
Venerable Bede	Historia ecclesiastica gentis Anglorum (a fragment)	appr. 731 AD	0.70 (0.77)	0.98
Thomas Aquinas	Summa Theologiae (a fragment)	1265–1274	0.71 (0.81)	0.90
Dante Alighieri	De Monarchia	1312 – 1313	0.73 (0.81)	0.94

3. Word order entropy at the level of (co-)dependencies

3.1. A probabilistic typology of languages based on word order entropy

This section discusses a language classification based on word order entropy. Figure 2 presents the mean entropy scores for the languages in the UD corpora. Several languages with small frequencies were excluded (Buryat, Cantonese, Korean, Kurmanji, Sanskrit and Swedish Sign Language). The higher the score, the more variable the word order is on average in the given language. The horizontal axis represents the average entropy of the head-dependent patterns. The vertical axis shows the average entropy in the order of co-dependents (SO/OS and OX/XO, where X stands for oblique). The entropy values were first computed for each dependency, and then averaged in every language. Trying out combinations of other parameters (e.g. entropy of function words or clauses) did not reveal additional interesting patterns or clusters. The reason is that most of the entropy values are positively correlated.⁶

Figure 2 shows that quite a few languages have high entropy on both dimensions (the top right corner). These are morphologically rich European languages (Ancient Greek, Latin, Basque, Finnic, Slavic, Dutch and German). They are followed by the Romance, North Germanic and Semitic languages, which have moderate scores. Notably, if languages have very low entropy, they have either low variation of the head-dependent patterns, or low variation of the co-dependent patterns, but not both. In particular, the Altaic and Dravidian languages and Japanese have very low entropy of head-dependent patterns, but the orders of co-dependents allow for some variability (cf. Jamashita & Chang 2000). In contrast, Mandarin, Irish, Coptic and English have rigid orders of co-dependents, but moderately rigid orders of heads and dependents. One may wonder if there exists a language in the world that allows no variation in word order at all.

⁶ See the Supplementary Materials. An exception is the position of subordinators, which is highly variable in low-entropy Mandarin Chinese, and to some extent in Vietnamese, Indic and Dravidian languages. In contrast, subordinators tend to be rigid in the other languages, most of which are have more variable word orders in general. As a consequence, there are negative correlations between the entropy values of subordinators and most of the other dependencies. According to Diessel (2001), languages with flexible position of adverbial clauses usually have adverbial subordinators in the beginning of the subordinate clause. This observation is fully supported by the UD data. Variable and final adverbial subordinators are only observed in the languages where the adverbial clauses always precede the main clause. For complement clauses and complementizers, the picture is not so clear, however.

Figure 2. Mean head-dependent order entropy and co-dependent entropy in the UD corpora.

The vertical dimension reflects mostly the variation in the SO entropy because the entropy of OX is higher than 0.6 in most languages (with the exception of Mandarin, Coptic and Irish). A remarkable thing is that the ancient Indo-European languages (Ancient Greek, Gothic, Latin and Old Church Slavonic) are located at or near the very top of the chart. A possible explanation is the growing analyticity in Indo-European (Dixon 1994: 183–184). Notably, Lithuanian, an extremely conservative Indo-European language as far as the nominal declension system is concerned (Erhart 1987: 129), has the highest score on the vertical dimension.

There is a common view that rigid word order can ‘step in’ when there are no morphological cues that help to disambiguate between the main arguments, and that the availability of case morphology is associated with more flexible word order. This relationship is well-known in linguistics (e.g. Sapir 1921: 66; Jakobson 1936[1971]: 28). For example, Blake (2001: 15) considers word order ‘an alternative to case marking’ in languages like English, Indonesian, Thai and Vietnamese. Those languages in which the main arguments (A and O) are not distinguishable by means of case flagging or indexing will tend to have on average more rigid word order of the arguments than the languages in which A and O are distinguishable. Futrell et al. (2015) formulate different corpus-induced measures of word order entropy and show that the languages with flexible word order tend to have case marking. Experimental support of this idea is also available (e.g. Fedzechkina et al. 2016).

Although this idea is common knowledge, it has not been tested systematically, to the best of my knowledge. To fill in this gap, I computed for each language the number of nouns that were identical in the subject and object functions, and in the position of the object and oblique nominal phrase. Case marking with adpositions was taken into account on a par with case inflections, so that the form *of John* was just as different from *John* as the Russian genitive/accusative form *Ivan-a* is different from the nominative form *Ivan*. Only non-plural forms were taken into account, i.e. those that were not marked as ‘Plural’ in the morphological properties slot. The analyses revealed very little overlap between object forms and oblique forms. The languages differ mostly in the degree to which they distinguish formally the subject from the object. This variation can be seen in Figure 3, where the proportion of formally identical subject and objects per lemma is plotted against the entropy of subject and object in a given language.⁷ Overall, one can see a negative correlation between the average confusability of the subject and object and the entropy of their order. A Generalized Additive Model with the genera as random intercepts (the families were not found to be worth including in the model) shows a non-linear negative effect displayed as the curved line in Figure 3 ($edf = 2.8$, $p = 0.0003$). The shaded area is the 95% confidence band. The model explains the data well (83.1% of deviance, i.e. variation is explained and R^2 is

⁷ Some comments are due. German has very many confusable forms because the determiners (articles, etc.) were not taken into account. English does not have perfect confusability score because it allows to use some oblique case forms to be used as core argument, e.g. *While Mary’s dream was to become a scientist, Jane’s was to marry a rich man*. Also, the names of companies, restaurants, basilicas, etc. (Papa John’s, St. Peter’s) can contain the genitive. Judging from the corpus data, written Japanese has almost no confusable forms, although a substantial share of case markers can be omitted in casual conversations (e.g. Kurumada & Jaeger 2015).

0.74).⁸ The model output can be accessed in the Supplementary Materials. Importantly, the correlation is between continuous variables, rather than binary features, such as [+/- case] or [+/- free word order]. This kind of relationships can only be tested on the basis of corpora.

Figure 3. Negative correlation between SO entropy and the proportion of identical S and O forms.

⁸ These numbers conceal the fact that some part of explained deviance may be due to the adjustments made to the individual genera (random intercepts). According to a likelihood ratio test, the R^2 of the model with both the confusability variable and the genera in comparison with the ‘null’ model with the genera only is 0.38. This is a substantial improvement.

The horizontal dimension of Figure 2, which shows the head-dependent entropy, is more difficult to explain. The right-hand part of the plot can be interpreted in terms of morphological richness and syntheticity, where the more synthetic languages tend to be on the right, while the analytic languages tend to be located close to the middle. There also seems to be a correlation between the horizontal and vertical dimensions. However, the left-hand part of the figure with very low entropy includes verb-final languages (Turkish, Japanese, etc.), which have rich morphology (e.g. Hawkins 2014: 139–146). The low variation of the head-dependent orders in verb-final languages may be another manifestation of their ‘tight fit’ with regard to argument and predicate frame differentiation (Hawkins 2014: Section 7.2). OV languages usually have a morphological case system, narrow semantic range of basic grammatical relationships, no raising or wh-extractions. All these restrictions, together with rigid word order, help the hearer to identify the argument structure early, so that there is no need to make corrections after the verb comes.

3.2. Entropy of individual word order patterns

This section discusses variation of the word order patterns within and across languages. In order to take into account the hierarchical structure of the UD corpora, where some languages are represented by several subcorpora, and some genera are represented by several languages, I first computed the measures for each corpus, then computed the mean for each language. After that, the average measure for every genus was computed. Finally, I averaged the entropy scores across the genera. The resulting scores represent the average intra-linguistic variability of the word order patterns. In addition, the standard deviations were computed. They are based on the average proportions of the dependent element being before the head (e.g. the average proportion of auxiliaries before the main verb in a genus), and of the SO and OX order. These proportions were first computed for each subcorpus, then averaged for each language, and finally for each genus. On the basis of the mean proportions in each genus, the standard deviations were computed. They represent the cross-linguistic variability of the word order patterns.

These two types of variability, intra-linguistic and cross-linguistic, are shown in Figure 4. The horizontal axis in Figure 4 displays the average entropy, or intra-linguistic variation of the twenty-four word order patterns. The patterns on the left-hand side have low entropy. This means that the order is fixed in most languages. For example, a language has either prepositions or postpositions. The right-hand side of the plot contains the word orders with greater intra-linguistic variability. In an individual language, the position of pronominal objects and obliques, adverbial clauses and adverbial modifiers of verbs, obliques with regard to objects and predicates tends to be the most flexible, whereas the position of complementizers, adverbial subordinators and adpositions is rigid in most languages. Various modifiers of nouns (adjectival and nominal modifiers, determiners, and attributive clauses) usually have limited variability, as well as auxiliaries, copulas, pronominal subjects, complement and subject clauses. Nominal subjects and numeral modifiers are more ‘fidgety’.

The vertical axis in Figure 4 shows the standard deviations of the average proportions of the word orders specified by the labels, and represents the cross-generic variability of those proportions. Adpositions, adjectival modifiers, subordinators, auxiliaries, objects, as well as attributive, complement and subject clauses, display substantial cross-linguistic variation. In contrast, the languages agree with regard to the position of subjects, determiners, numerals and adverbial modifiers.

Figure 4. Cross-linguistic variability (vertical axis) and intra-linguistic entropy (horizontal axis) of selected syntactic dependencies from the UD corpora.

This information has important implications for word order typology as a domain of inquiry. The patterns in the top left corner of the plot include the ones that have received the greatest attention in the literature: adpositions, nominal objects, adjectives and nominal modifiers (predominantly genitives). This figure explains why: these patterns exhibit high cross-linguistic variation, but low intra-linguistic variation, which makes them perfect candidates for typological investigations based on reference grammars. Although this bias is understandable from a practical point of view, it also means a considerable data reduction when one focuses only on those features (cf. Wälchli 2009).

The patterns in the bottom, on the left, may be less interesting for language classification because they exhibit less variation, but they are still important for typological purposes because they allow us to formulate universal statements about languages. Most languages tend to put subjects before objects. This is not new (e.g. Hawkins 2014: 5). What is

more interesting, perhaps, is the very low variation in the position of the pronominal subjects with regard to the verbs within a language, which is lower than the variation in the position of the nominal subjects. This may have to do with the fact that nominal subjects can be used to introduce new information, as in the example *In the middle of the room stood a table*. In contrast, pronominal subjects are topical and given, and are used before the verb in topic-first languages (cf. Givón 1984: Section 6.5; see also Section 5.1). Also, the order of numerals, determiners and adverbial modifiers of adjectives is to some extent similar cross-linguistically. They tend to occur predominantly before their heads. However, this is an artefact of the UD language sample. According to Dryer (2013a, b), numerals and demonstratives (a subclass of determiners) exhibit strong areal patterns. They are pre-nominal in Eurasia (where most of the corpora come from), but can be post-nominal in some other areas, such as Africa and Southeast Asia. The low intra-linguistic entropy of determiners, however, is quite informative. It can be explained by the high entrenchment of the combinations of determiners and nouns due to high frequency (see Section 5.1).

Finally, the obliques and adverbials are located on the right, which means that they exhibit high entropy in individual languages. This variability can be explained by their different functions in discourse. For example, adverbial clauses of condition tend to precede the main clause, while adverbial clauses of result and purpose usually follow the main clause (Diessel 2001). This is explained by universal cognitive and discourse-pragmatic factors, in particular, by iconicity of temporal order. Similar explanations can also be offered for obliques and adverbial modifiers of verbs. For instance, a closer look at English, Finnish and Russian obliques and adverbials reveals striking similarities between the languages. The adjuncts on the left from the predicate are often those which introduce causal links with the previous discourse (e.g. *therefore, thus*), mark the relative position of the statement in the rhetorical structure (e.g. *also, moreover, finally*), express the epistemic stance towards the entire proposition (e.g. *possibly, reportedly, certainly*) or the speaker's emotional attitude (e.g. *hopefully*). The adjuncts on the right often have the directional meaning (*go + abroad, to the market*), expressing the potential outcome of the action (Author, In preparation). These patterns have received less attention in typology than the others, but they are also important for cross-linguistic generalizations because they allow us to formulate probabilistic universals based on the general discourse-pragmatic principles.

To summarize, although word order typology has mainly focused on the patterns with low intra-linguistic variability and high cross-linguistic variability, we also need to explore the other patterns. One can expect that the high-entropy patterns can be particularly valuable for providing a window into the universal processing and communicative biases.

4. Word order entropy at the lexically specific level

In the previous section it was mentioned that high entropy of particular word order patterns may be explained by their diverse functions in discourse. This functional diversity can be approximated by taking into account the individual wordforms. For example, *on Monday* is typically a temporal adjunct, whereas *therefore* is a causal adverbial modifier. To what extent will the variability of the word order patterns change if we compute the entropy on the lexical level? Will we see a totally different classification of languages? The goal of this section is to answer these questions.

For this purpose, I took large news corpora of eleven languages (100,000 sentences in each) from the Leipzig Corpora Collection and parsed them with the *udpipe* R package. The languages were Arabic, Basque, English, Finnish, Hindi, Indonesian, Irish, Mandarin, Russian, Tamil and Turkish. All of them belong to different genera. The reason for using the additional larger corpora is that one needs high frequencies in order to obtain reliable estimates of entropy for individual lexemes. Next, I extracted the head-dependent patterns, using the same approach as outlined in Section 2, plus the information about the wordform of the dependent element, e.g. *big* + Noun, where *big* is an adjectival modifier *amod*, which modifies a noun. This type of patterns will be called here lexically specific dependencies. Only the dependencies in the simple clause were considered. The dependencies related to complex clauses were excluded because it is difficult to imagine that the lexical predicate of the subordinate clause is relevant for the semantic and pragmatic function of the clause.

The wordforms of the dependent elements also included adpositions with the function ‘case’ because these functional units play an important role in determining the function of the

lexeme in a sentence. For example, *John*, *of John*, *John's*, *to John*, etc. were all considered different wordforms and were treated separately, similar to Russian *Ivan*, *Ivan-a* 'I.-ACC/GEN', *Ivan-u* 'Ivan-DAT', *k Ivan-u* 'to Ivan-DAT', etc. For each lexically specific dependency I computed the frequencies of occurrence of this wordform before and after the head (e.g. the form *table* as a nominal subject before and after the predicate). On the basis of those frequencies, I computed the measure of entropy for each individual wordform using the formula and method described in Section 2. In order to obtain reliable results, I only included the wordforms with the frequency above 20.

Figure 5 displays the mean entropy measures for the 16 dependencies computed in two different ways. The horizontal axis shows the mean entropies at the level of abstract dependencies of the type discussed in Section 3. The vertical axis displays the entropy based on the lexically specific dependencies. The entropy scores were first computed for each wordform, then averaged for each dependency (e.g. *det_Noun*, *amod_Noun*, etc.) and finally averaged across the languages.

Importantly, the entropies based on the abstract dependencies are higher than the wordform-based ones, as one can see from the values on the axes. This means that some part of the variation can be explained by the variation between individual wordforms. At the same time, there is a high correlation between the two sets of scores: $r = 0.978133$, $p < 0.0001$. This means that the entropy-based classification of the languages remains essentially the same, regardless of the level of granularity.

The languages in which the averaged dependencies show the largest differences are Finnish (the difference between the mean abstract dependency entropy and mean lexically informed entropy is 0.24) and Russian (0.23). The smallest differences are observed, as one would expect, in the low-entropy languages Hindi and Tamil (0.04 both).

Figure 5. Mean head-dependent entropy in a language. Horizontal axis: mean head-dependent entropy without lexical information; vertical axis: mean head-dependent entropy with lexical information.

As for the individual dependencies, consider Figure 6. Again, the horizontal axis shows the mean entropies at the level of abstract dependencies, whereas the vertical axis displays the mean entropies at the level of wordforms, averaged first in a given language, and then averaged across the languages.

Figure 6. Mean entropies of dependencies averaged across eleven languages. Horizontal axis: mean head-dependent entropy without lexical information; vertical axis: mean head-dependent entropy with lexical information.

Again, we find that the entropies are strongly correlated: $r = 0.91$, $p < 0.0001$. The adpositions, auxiliaries, adjectives and nominal modifiers of other nouns have low entropies regardless of the method. The highest entropy scores on both axes are observed for the obliques and for the adverbial modifiers of verbs, similar to the results reported in Section 3.2. However, the correspondence is not perfect. On average, the dependencies that show the greatest differences between the entropies with and without lexical information are *advmod_Verb* (the difference is 0.24), *det_Noun* (0.23) and *nummod_Noun* (0.21). These are the dependencies where one can expect the greatest functional specialization. This is not surprising. Some examples of adverbial modifiers of verbs were given in the previous

section. Their position often depends on their function. As for determiners, they constitute a very heterogeneous category: demonstrative, possessive, negative and indefinite pronouns, articles, etc. Their positions with regard to the head noun can vary. For example, in Irish, the definite article and possessive pronouns precede the noun, e.g. *an* ‘the’ + *fear* ‘man’ and *do* ‘your’ + *chara* ‘friend’, whereas the demonstrative pronouns follow it, e.g. *an* ‘the’ + *bhean* ‘woman’ + *seo* ‘this’. As for numeral modifiers, they can also perform diverse functions. For example, they can specify the quantity, e.g. 5 books, but appear in dates (e.g. the year 2019), telephone numbers (e.g. the emergency number 112) or addresses (e.g. 10 Downing Street). One can argue how to classify these instances in a corpus, of course. The dependencies with the smallest differences are *aux_Verb* and *nsubjPRON_Pred* (both 0.04). They also display little entropy on average.

If we look at specific languages and individual dependencies, the differences between the approaches can be quite striking, however. For instance, English nominal modifiers are often genitives can be both and after the head noun, e.g. *the emperor’s new dress* and *the new dress of the emperor*, but if their position is strictly determined by the type of the genitive construction: the Saxon genitive always precedes the noun, and the Norman genitive always follows it. This is why the nominal modifiers have much lower entropy when the form is taken into account in comparison with their entropy when the wordforms do not matter: 0.024 vs. 0.524.

The highest discrepancy between abstract and lexically-specific entropy is observed for the Mandarin adpositions (0.990 vs. 0.01). They can be postpositions, prepositions, or elements of circumpositions, but their place with regard to the head noun depends very strictly on the lexeme. For example, the locative marker *zài* ‘at, in’ and the directional marker *dào* ‘to’ are always used before the noun, whereas the possessive markers *de* and *zhī* are used after the noun. Next come numeral modifiers in Basque (0.93 vs. 0.19), where the numeral *bat* ‘one’ in different forms, unlike all other cardinal numerals, takes the postnominal position (Hualde & Ortiz de Urbina 2003: 118). This is a highly frequent numeral, which is also the indefinite article with the meaning ‘a certain’. It is difficult to distinguish between the functions in the corpus data. Similarly, Indonesian contains different determiners (0.87 vs. 0.29). Quantifiers like *semua* ‘all’ and *beberapa* ‘some’ are used before the head noun, while possessive and demonstrative pronouns follow the head noun. The smallest differences are observed in those cases where the entropy based on abstract dependencies is close to 0.

There are also some cases when the lexically specific entropy is in fact higher than the entropy based on the abstract dependencies, although the difference is usually very small. For example, English pronominal subjects have on average slightly higher lexically specific entropy due to the pronouns *something* and *nothing*, which are often used in the construction with the presentative adverb *there*, e.g. *there is something in the air tonight*. However, this variation nearly disappears when the entropy is computed at the level of the abstract dependency because of the high-frequency personal pronouns, which exhibit almost no variability. Such discrepancies also observed in the other pronominal arguments (subjects and modifiers of nouns) and in adpositions in some languages. Thus, the presence of high-frequency exemplars with low variability tends to decrease the entropy on the level of abstract dependencies, whereas the presence of functional subcategories is responsible for its increase.

From all this follows that the lexically ‘naïve’ estimates of entropy give a reliable idea of the general magnitude of word order variation in a language, although they overestimate the variation. This works only when many dependencies are taken, however. If one performs a classification that involves a small selection of word order patterns, he or she should be well advised to check the subcategories of dependencies and individual lexemes.

5. Functional explanations of word order entropy

5.1. Causal factors that influence word order variation

One can think of several factors that influence the variation of word order patterns. One of them has already been discussed. Low entropy of word order helps to disambiguate potentially confusable arguments. One should also mention the typical information-theoretic role of constituents. If a constituent frequently performs a particular role, which is associated with a specific position in discourse, then the position of the constituent will also be fixed.

For example, topical, non-surprising and given information tends to have a fixed position in discourse. It is either before the verb, close to the left, like in Mandarin or Russian, or after the verb, more to the right in languages like Ute or Early Biblical Hebrew (Givón 1984: Section 6.5). At the same time, subjects are often associated with givenness and topicality, especially transitive ones (Du Bois et al. 2003; Lambrecht 1994). Therefore, one can expect the subjects to have a fixed position. Objects, in contrast, can introduce new referents, but do not always do so. In fact, they are frequently topical, definite and old (cf. Dalrymple and Nikolaeva 2011: 172; Author XXXX). We have seen already that pronominal subjects exhibit little variation in their position with regard to the predicate (see Section 3.2). This can be explained by their topical role.

Another important factor seems to be grammaticalization, which limits the syntagmatic variability of linguistic units, i.e. the ease with which a word can be shifted around in context (Lehmann 2015: 167). For example, full verbs are more flexible than auxiliaries with regard to the verbal phrase with which they combine. Compare the verb ‘have’ in Classical Latin and Italian. In Classical Latin, the parts of the construction *epistulam scriptam habeo* ‘I have a letter written’ could appear in any order. Compare this with Italian *ho scritto una lettera* ‘I have written a letter’, where the auxiliary always precedes the main verb (Lehmann 2015: 168). From this follows that more grammaticalized functional elements should have more rigid positions with regard to their heads (i.e. nouns for adpositions, main verbs for auxiliaries) than less grammaticalized ones (e.g. nominal arguments or adjuncts). But grammaticalization itself is only an umbrella term for a bunch of different processes; it is not a causal factor. So, why are more grammaticalized units more fixed positionally?

In my opinion (see also Bybee 2002), the lack of variability of function words can be explained by the entrenchment of frequently occurring combinations of words. The combinations of function words with their heads are highly frequent. According to the usage-based view, frequent combinations of words become more entrenched and produced as chunks due to repetition. If these lexically specific chunks overlap with other chunks (e.g. *my car, my book, her book, her phone, this phone*, etc.), the pattern will be schematized as abstract constructions (e.g. [Determiner + Noun]), which can serve as the basis for emergence of syntactic constituents (Bybee 2002). Therefore, more frequent combinations of words will display a more rigid order than less frequent ones. Since frequency is a driving force of

grammaticalization, we can expect that function elements, which are more grammaticalized, will also exhibit a more rigid order.

Moreover, one should consider processing constraints. In particular, the length of constituents has been shown to play an important role in word order. The preference to put long phrases after short ones was observed already in the classical rhetorical tradition (cf. Behaghel 1909–10: 137–138). Behaghel (1909–10) provided a first systematic account based on texts in Greek, Latin and German and called this preference *Das Gesetz der Wachsenden Glieder* (the law of the growing elements). According to Hawkins (1994, 2014), human parsers prefer short constituent recognition domains. In a nutshell, these domains are minimized when shorter constituents, which are faster to process, are placed closer to the head than longer ones. This principle is known as “Minimize Domains”, or Early Immediate Constituents. Another principle is “Maximize Online Processing”, which helps to avoid garden path effects and delays in online property assignment. All this can be important for word order variation. For instance, VO languages tend to minimize domains and maximize online processing by putting complement clauses after the predicate. At the same time, the position of shorter dependencies (e.g. one-word adjectives) is less crucial for domain minimization (Hawkins 2014: 101). This may affect the potential for variability of the corresponding word order patterns.

These factors and principles can be in conflict. For instance, the position of short elements are less important for the principle “Minimize Domains”, which can increase the variability of their position before or after the head. At the same time, short elements can also be highly frequent, which means that their position will be fixed due to entrenchment and chunking. As was shown in Section 3.2, short functional elements (e.g. adpositions, auxiliaries and subordinators) usually have a rigid position in a language, as well as long clauses (with the exception of adverbial clauses). The position of mid-length constituents is usually more flexible. In the remaining part of this section, I will present a case study where these opposing motivations are tested on corpus data.

5.2. The role of entrenchment and heaviness in explaining word order entropy

In order to test the ideas discussed in the previous section, I fitted a regression model on the data with the head-dependent patterns in the UD corpora. The entropy of a specific word order in an individual UD corpus was treated as the response variable. There were three categorical predictors, which are described below.

The first predictor described the functions of the dependencies, which were classified into four categories:

- function elements (adpositions, subordinators, auxiliaries, copulas, determiners);
- core arguments and functionally similar clauses (subjects, objects, complement and subject clauses);
- obliques and adverbials, which were called for shortness ‘adjuncts’ (oblique nominal and pronominal phrases, adverbial modifiers, adverbial clauses);
- modifiers of nouns and adjectives in a nominal phrase, with the exception of determiners (adjectival modifiers, attributive clauses, numerals and nominal modifiers of nouns).

Following the considerations discussed in the previous section, I expected function words to exhibit the lowest entropy due to their high level of entrenchment. I also expected adjuncts (i.e. adverbials and obliques) to have the highest entropy, due to their multifunctionality.

Heaviness was operationalized in a binary way, whether the dependency was a clause or not. This has to do with the fact that the lengths in orthographic words are difficult to compare cross-linguistically because the word is a problematic comparative concept (see the discussion in Section 6). At the same time, it is uncontroversial that clausal constituents represent the heaviest elements cross-linguistically. Their position is determined by the general processing principles (Hawkins 1994, 2014), which were mentioned above.

Importantly, the previous studies show that the effect of length depends on whether the language is predominantly OV or VO. In order to take that into account, I created three categories, based on the proportion of OV in the language. The distribution is strongly bimodal, so it was useful to encode this as a categorical variable. The first category was “VO”, with the proportions of nominal objects followed by predicates ranging from 0 to 20%. The second category was “Flexible”, with the proportions from 20 to 80%. Note that this

intermediate category was biased towards the languages with a mild preference towards VO. The third category was “OV”, with the proportions from 80 to 100%.

Next, a linear mixed model was fitted, with the function, heaviness and the object-verb order as predictors. I tested the pairwise interactions between the function and the OV/VO order, and between heaviness and the OV/VO order, in order to check whether the effects of the function and length vary in OV and VO languages.⁹ These interactions are highly significant. The language, genus and dependency type were tested as random intercepts. Only the language and dependency type proved to be useful, according to the likelihood ratio tests. The table of coefficients and other information are provided in the Supplementary Materials.

Figure 7 shows the effect of the functional type of dependencies on the entropy for OV, VO and flexible word order. Not surprisingly, the flexible languages have the highest entropy values across arguments, adjuncts and nominal phrase elements, whereas the OV languages have the lowest values. Adjuncts have the highest entropy, whereas function words have the lowest entropy, also in the OV languages. In the flexible and VO languages, we observe the following order: adjuncts with the highest entropy are followed by arguments, then by nominal phrase elements and finally by function words.

A post-hoc analysis of all pairs of estimates (see the Supplementary Materials) shows that there are no statistically significant differences between the functions in the OV languages. In the VO and flexible languages, function words are significantly different from adjuncts and arguments, but not from NP elements. Arguments, adjuncts and NP elements are significantly more variable in the VO and flexible languages than in the OV languages. There are no differences between function words in the three language types.

⁹ In addition, an interaction between the function and heaviness was tested on the data without function elements (since they cannot be clauses). The interaction was not significant ($p = 0.49$).

Figure 7. Interaction between the function type of dependencies and the order of O and V.

Next, let us interpret the interaction between the heaviness (clause vs. non-clause) and the order of object and predicate, which is displayed in Figure 8. The plot suggests that the heaviness effect is observed only in the VO and flexible languages. The clauses are indeed less variable than non-clauses, although they still exhibit substantial variation. In the OV languages, we observe a reversed order: the clauses are slightly more variable than non-clauses, but the difference is very small. The post-hoc tests indicate that the differences between clauses and non-clauses are not statistically significant. At the same time, the ANOVA tests show that the interaction in general is statistically significant and should therefore be kept in the model (see the Supplementary Materials). This means that the effect of heaviness indeed varies across the languages with different OV/VO orders.

Figure 8. Interaction between heaviness and the order of O and V.

To summarize, we can make the following conclusions. First, not surprisingly, the languages without a clear preference for OV or VO also exhibit the highest entropy in all conditions. The predominantly OV languages display the lowest entropy.

Second, function words have the lowest entropy in all languages, and adjuncts have the highest, although there are significant differences only in the VO and flexible languages. Therefore, entrenchment due to high frequency can make a difference, provided there is enough variability in a language. The adjuncts have the highest entropy, most probably, due to their multifunctionality.

Third, there is a significant difference in the heaviness effect on entropy between the OV languages and the VO and flexible languages. There is a tendency in the latter to have lower entropy of clauses in comparison with non-clauses, whereas the OV languages display hardly any difference. This supports the processing-related explanation, which was mentioned in Section 5.1. According to Hawkins (1994, 2014), object clauses with the subordinator in the initial position, as is the case in VO languages, tend to follow the main

clause. This order makes the processing optimal based on both principles, “Minimize Domains”, and “Maximize Online Processing”. As for OV languages, these principles are in conflict. Therefore, there is no perfect solution, although typological data suggest that the postverbal position is the more popular one (Schmidtke-Bode & Diessel 2017). The same logic applies to relative clauses (Hawkins 2014: Ch. 7), which are usually postnominal in VO languages, but can be either postnominal or prenominal in OV languages.

Importantly, Hawkins’s principles were formulated on the level of languages and their preferred strategy. The regression model shows that the heaviness effect in the VO and flexible languages is discernible also at the level of usage tokens and probabilistic tendencies, and that there is even a weak mirror image of the effect in the OV languages. Probably, there is too little variation in general in the OV languages in the first place for the heaviness effects to be visible in language use.¹⁰

6. Conclusions and perspectives

The aim of the present paper was to show the importance of token frequencies for the main tasks of typological research: language classification and identification and explanation of cross-linguistic generalizations. The first case study reported a classification of languages based on their average entropy scores. The data show that morphologically rich European VO and OV languages (e.g. Basque, Estonian, German and Slovak) tend to have high entropy of head-dependent orders. Notably, the ancient Indo-European languages (Ancient Greek, Gothic, Latin, and Old Church Slavonic) have very high word order variation. Their more analytical descendants and relatives (with the exception of some Slavic languages) tend to exhibit lower entropy. Syntheticity, which is usually accompanied by abundance of grammatical markers, seems to be a necessary, but not sufficient condition for high entropy. This is so because morphologically rich Asian OV languages have a very fixed head –

¹⁰ This does not mean, of course, that there are no heaviness effects in usage in OV languages, but these effects manifest themselves in the order of co-dependent elements, e.g. objects and obliques (Hawkins 2014: 96–98), not in the order of heads and dependents, which is analyzed here.

dependent order. It seems that there are no languages with very rigid head–dependent orders and very rigid orders of co-dependent subjects, objects and obliques with regard to one another. This may be due to the necessity to have some means for the management of information flow in discourse.

The entropy of SO/OS order correlates significantly with the proportion of distinct forms of nominal subjects and objects in a language. This supports the idea that low word order entropy has a disambiguating function. This idea has been around since time immemorial, but the regression model presented in Section 3.1 adds a new flavour to this old idea. Namely, it demonstrates that the correlation is observed when the formal distinctness and word order variability are treated as probabilistic, gradable parameters. This has not been shown before. This demonstrates how amazingly subtle and fine-grained can grammar adjustments be for the purposes of efficient communication.

As for the position of heads and dependents, we observe a correlation between syntheticity and entropy only for VO or flexible languages. Contrary to what one could expect, the predominantly OV languages, which are far from being isolating, exhibit very low entropy of heads and dependents. This can be explained by the ‘tight fit’ of arguments for the purposes of early and correct recognition of the constituents, which is required when the verb appears only in the end of a clause.

The traditional word order typology is based on those dependencies that exhibit low intra-linguistic variability and high cross-linguistic variation, e.g. the order of adpositions and nouns, nominal objects and verbs, adjectives and nouns. This does not mean that the other types are irrelevant, however. The dependencies with low cross-linguistic and intra-linguistic variability represent valuable material for processing universals, e.g. the pronominal subject in most languages tends to be in front of the predicate. The dependencies that exhibit high intra-linguistic variation in all or most languages, e.g. adverbial modifiers and clauses, are also relevant for typology. They can help us to discover those universals that are based on universal discourse-processing constraints.

The next question was whether the semantic and pragmatic function of different word classes within the dependencies may explain the variability or rigidity of the word order. This was checked on a sample of eleven languages represented by large corpora of online news. Partly, this is indeed so. The average entropy is lower when the individual wordforms are

taken into account, especially for some dependencies, such as determiners, numeral modifiers and adverbial modifiers. The reason is the functional diversity of those categories. However, there still remains a large amount of variation. Overall, there is a strong positive correlation between the lexically specific and non-specific measures of entropy for the languages and the individual dependencies.

The paper also presented the universal factors that influence the variability of word order. In contrast to the previous explanations, which employed single parameters, such as configurationality, branching direction or head-dependent order – which may still be useful as purely descriptive measures – I believe that the **explanation** of word order directionality and variability can be found directly in general cognitive and communicative principles, which determine language use. No additional theoretical layers are required. In addition to disambiguation, which was mentioned earlier, one can also name optimization of processing in terms of minimization of domains and avoidance of ambiguities, and entrenchment of word combinations due to high frequency, with the subsequent schematization of the patterns and grammaticalization of the units involved.

These factors were investigated in a regression model based on the UD corpora, which modelled the effects of length, function and predominant order of verb and object on word order entropy of head-dependent patterns. The model revealed the following cline:

(3) Function elements < Modifiers of a noun < Arguments < Adjuncts

where the function elements have the lowest entropy, and adjuncts (oblique phrases and adverbials) have the highest entropy in the languages where there is sufficient word order variation. I argue that function words are the least flexible because these unit in combination with their heads are highly entrenched due to high frequency. Adjuncts are the most variable because of their multifunctionality. In addition, there is an effect of heaviness. Clauses, which are the heaviest constituents, tend to have less freedom than lighter elements and usually occur after the head (the verb or noun in the main clause) in the VO and flexible languages. There is no strong effect in the OV languages, however. This is a novel finding because these

preferences were formulated and explained on the level of languages as types, rather than usage tokens.

Thus, the token-based approach provides us with new criteria for typological classification, ideas for cross-linguistic generalizations, an opportunity for analyses at different levels of lexical granularity, and a testing ground for universal functional constraints. We can also reformulate some of the existing type-based generalizations at the level of tokens. This helps us to understand better the interaction between language use and language structure, which can manifest itself either as ‘soft’ or ‘hard’ constraints in individual languages (Bresnan et al. 2001).

In addition to these advantages, there are also other benefits. In particular, one can use mixed types of languages and linguistic categories, without forcing them into Procrustean beds. The researcher is no longer required to group languages into types, using some arbitrary cut-off points. Moreover, the token-based approach will force typologists to formulate their generalizations and comparative concepts more precisely, in a way that they can be tested on corpus data. The task for future research is to include various semantic, pragmatic and structural variables in order to test and induce universal correlations and implicational relationships directly from usage events, in line with Multivariate and Distributional Typology (Bickel 2010; Bickel 2015).

There are a few challenges that should be mentioned, as well. First of all, we need corpora representing a large number of diverse languages with rich and maximally uniform linguistic annotation, including semantic and pragmatic variables. At present, the largest collection of multilingual texts is the parallel corpus of the Bible translations (Mayer & Cysouw 2014), which currently contains more than 1850 translations that represent more than 1400 languages (i.e. unique ISO-codes). However, they do not have any linguistic annotation, with the exception of information about verse alignment (see the Supplementary Materials). Similarly, the Leipzig Corpora Collection only contains sentences. In contrast, the UD corpora have a bias towards the Indo-European and Eurasian languages, which might explain some of the cross-linguistic tendencies reported in Section 3.2, but contain a lot of useful linguistic information, such as syntactic functions and morphological categories. Multi-CAST (Haig & Schnell 2016a) has semantic annotation of NPs and their syntactic roles and even information about zero elements in discourse.

The examination of the lexically specific dependencies has also revealed that some word order variability is due to different subclasses of words, which have different positional preferences. For example, different types of determiners and adverbial modifiers exhibit different preferences in some languages in the sample. This makes one wonder, which level of granularity is optimal for cross-linguistic comparisons. A possible solution could be as follows: the researcher should choose the level of abstraction at which the differences between this level and the more lexically or functionally specific one are minimized across the languages in the sample.

There are some conceptual issues, as well. Traditionally, the fundamental unit of analysis in corpus linguistics is the word. One speaks of key words, key key words, word frequency lists, etc. The main and usually the only criterion for delimiting words is orthography. However, since this criterion is problematic (Haspelmath 2011), analyses based on orthographic words can be misleading. In fact, there have been some practical attempts to take this into account. For example, some UD corpora provide information about multiword expressions (MWE), such as *New York* and *in spite of*, both analysed as a whole and at the level of individual components. Some corpora offer a two-tier analysis of clitics, as one word and as two units, e.g. Italian *inquinandolo* = *inquinando* “polluting” + *lo* “it”, leaving the decision to the linguist which solution to use (or both).

Still, in spite of these practical and theoretical challenges, one can be optimistic about the future of the token-based approach. The number of diverse corpora and corpus tools is increasing rapidly. One can also hope that cooperation between typologists and corpus linguists will result in new insights and creative solutions of conceptual problems.

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